

Mechanical, Dielectric, Linear and Nonlinear Optical Characterization of Pure and Lanthanum Doped Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate Single Crystals

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Abstract

Single crystals of pure and Lanthanum doped Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate were grown by slow evaporation solution growth technique. The cell parameters were determined using single crystal X-ray diffraction method. To improve the physical properties of the Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystal, Lanthanum dopant was added by 2 mol%. ICP studies confirm the presence of Lanthanum in the grown Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystal. Transparency range of the crystal was determined using UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer. The functional groups of pure and doped Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystals were analyzed by FT-IR spectroscopy. Using Vickers micro hardness tester, mechanical strength of the material was calculated. Dielectric studies of pure and doped Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate single crystals were carried out. NLO property of the grown material is confirmed by Kurtz Perry powder technique. The doped Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystal is found to have efficiency higher than that of pure Zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystal. Most of organic NLO materials have poor mechanical and thermal properties, resulting in the damage of crystal during processing. To avoid this drawback, a new type of NLO material has been grown from organic-inorganic complexes. L-Alanine crystals have increased attention for photo induced nonlinear optical effects and dispersion of the linear and nonlinear optical susceptibilities. In the present work, a systematic study has been carried out on the growth of pure and Lanthanum doped zinc L-Alanine Tartrate crystals.

Keywords: Nonlinear Optics, Amino acid, Organic Material.

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